

THE (CURRENT) STATE OF PRACTICE OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATION CULTURE IN FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the (current) practical situation of formation of communication culture among future foreign language teachers. We can also see that the problems of communication culture of future foreign language teachers have been studied by a number of pedagogic scientists from today's point of view. The formation of communication culture is important for the development of speech skills in people. As the main task of communication, it can be recognized that people form communication on the basis of the experience developed by a certain person, as a result of which the demands placed on individual experience are limited. Therefore, the culture of communication is an important factor in the development of a person, because in communication a person realizes his personal characteristics. It follows that it can be considered that the main functions of communication develop through communication.

INTRODUCTION

The modern approach to the field of education is to organize the process of formation of the personality of a highly educated specialist on the basis of the interaction and interpenetration of all types of education aimed at forming the general culture of a person. Analysis of the practice of formation of a future foreign language specialist allows us to emphasize that the teaching of foreign subjects should be focused on a comprehensive analysis of modern social problems. Development context of world culture; the culture of future specialists should be formed, attracting new creative thinking; the interaction of the subjects of the pedagogical process, including the cooperation of teachers and students, should create such a relationship environment that helps to develop qualities in future professionals in a higher education institution. An intelligent person; unity of professional and general culture of students should be aimed at developing independent acquisition of spiritual and moral values, creating the ground for realization of intellectual and spiritual potential of future specialists in their professional activities.

MAIN PART

Currently, the formation of communication culture among future foreign language teachers is of great importance. Not only teaching students a foreign language, but also teaching them to develop communication culture is of special importance as the main link of quality education today. In addition, the development of intercultural communication in foreign language learning is closely related to language teaching. The main goal of teaching a foreign language is not strictly defined in terms of mastering communication in a foreign language. Teachers must now also teach intercultural communication. It follows that new professional requirements should be imposed on teachers. If the teaching of foreign languages is not considered as the main linguistic task and it should be directed to the full mastery of the culture of communication, including its intercultural aspect, then the teachers need the knowledge, skills and they should also form skills together. It involves a broader task.

The development of communication culture made it possible to look at social psychology as a scientific discipline from a new perspective in the 60s. During these years, BD Parygin developed the concept of "mutual understanding" and defined communication as "at the same time as a process of interaction between individuals, as well as an information process, the attitude of people to each other and a complex and multifaceted process that can act as a process of their interaction is characterized as interaction and mutual understanding" and SL Rubinstein interpreted communication as the mutual understanding of people and described it as an indispensable condition for the success of people in their joint activities. VM Bekhterev believes that communication is a mechanism for forming a collective subject, i.e. a joint conduct of mutual activities, as well as a condition for preserving and disseminating individual experience, passing it on to generations, and ensuring the historical continuity of social values.

The analysis of the above-mentioned views of scientists allows us to generalize the main approaches to the concept of "communication".

1. Communication is considered as a relatively independent category, in which communication subjects act for each other only as epistemological objects (BFLomov, AGKovalyov, etc.).
2. Communication is characterized by transferring all elements of the "activity" category to it (ANLeontiev, MSKagan, KK, Platonov).
3. Communication is determined by the nature of social relations (VMBechterevev, LPBueva, etc.).

However, the classification of "activity" and "communication" is common to all approaches. Therefore, without talking about real communication, the communication process itself includes all other activities, practical interaction of people (joint work, play, study, etc.), and this interaction is an integral part of the mystery.

in modern science can be summarized as follows:

1. Communication culture is characterized as a process of exchanging information between people and establishing mutual understanding between them. Thoughts, feelings, experiences, opinions, knowledge, social values, experience, etc. act as information.
2. Communicative culture as one of the most important independent categories of psychology, the process of interaction, where the transfer of information is only a necessary condition for the flow of communication. The purpose of human communication is to establish mutual understanding, to establish mutual relations, to unite people within a certain society.
3. Communication is considered as one of the types of human activity or a type of social relations.

When expressing the types of communication, two main types of communication can be distinguished. This interesting approach, from the point of view of the characteristics of the content side of communication, inter-role (business) and interpersonal (free), a number of levels of communication are distinguished, which reflect the depth of the objective content of this process: level - speech statements to continue the conversation exchange; information level - constant information exchange of various characteristics; controversial and confessional level is the most reliable and indicates extreme sincerity. The following groups can be divided according to the content of communication and the task to be performed:

- a) the first is socially oriented communication, which implements social relations, the purpose of which is to organize social interaction.
- b) communication directed to the subject of the group, whose task is to organize the interaction of the group.
- v) the third group is person-oriented communication, which is carried out in two forms (GM Andreeva):
 - business-oriented, joint activity-oriented and essentially entity-oriented;
 - or "reveals relationships" as a type of communication.

Thus, debates arose among scientists on the issue of communication functions. However, in general - recognition of the gender and functionality of communication, MB Finko, based on the principles of structural analysis, identifies all possible functional situations in the structure of communication (SS). It is clear from this that, in accordance with goal setting, the following functions of communication can be counted: providing objective activity, communicating for the sake of communication, introducing another person to one's own values, getting to know another person's values.

Defining the formation of communication culture as an important factor in the development of society, the following social functions of communication can be indicated:

- 1 - organizes planning, coordination, social control, etc. of joint labor activities aimed at meeting the needs of society and its separate groups;
- 2 - members of society - a socio-psychological characteristic related to the needs of individuals, which constitute socialization, transmission of generational experience, etc.

DK Aminova and PM Jalilova pay particular attention to the distribution of communication functions in their works: information and communication, information transmission and regulation, and reception. Communicative implies mutual adaptation and regulation of behavior in a broad sense in the implementation of joint activities. The affective-communicative process is related to determining the emotional sphere of a person and changing his emotional state. At the same time, the main task of communication culture is to overcome the limitations of individual experience and create an opportunity for a person to master the experience developed by mankind.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we know very well that the language of the society expresses the character, thinking, outlook, and aspirations of the entire nation. Through language, people express their thoughts and feelings. It is used to communicate. Language is a means of communication between people, and its permanent task is to live in speech. The communicative function of language is so rich that it always encourages mutual respect in society and nature. We can also

see that the problems of communication culture of future foreign language teachers have been studied by a number of pedagogic scientists from today's point of view. The formation of communication culture is important for the development of speech skills in people. As the main task of communication, it can be recognized that people form communication on the basis of the experience developed by a certain person, as a result of which the demands placed on individual experience are limited. Therefore, communication culture is individual an important factor in its development, because in communication a person realizes his personal characteristics. It follows that it can be considered that the main functions of communication develop through communication.

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